

Mixed ligand complexes of iron-, cobalt- and nickel(II) with 2,3-dihydroxypyridine and some nitrogen donors

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Fe^{II}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} mixed ligand complexes of 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DHP) and some nitrogen donor ligands NH₃/CH₃NH₂/C₂H₅NH₂/Py have been synthesized.

2,3-Dihydroxypyridine (DHP) is a biologically important reagent¹ and its chelating tendency has been recognized by different workers². However, no work has been reported on the mixed ligand metal complexes of DHP. Lack of past studies and the fact that the mixed ligand complexes could be expected to be more biologically active³ than the binary complexes, prompted us to undertake the present work.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of mixed ligand complexes (Table 1) indicate that the metal, DHP and *N*-donor ligand ratio in each case is 1 : 2 : 2. The molar conductance values (2.2–4.6 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹) indicate their non-ionic nature.

Table 1. Thermal data of mixed ligand metal complexes*

Compd.	TG method Activation energy kJ mol ⁻¹	DTA method Δ <i>H</i> of endo. kJ mol ⁻¹	DSC method Δ <i>H</i> of endo. kJ mol ⁻¹
Fe(DHP) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂	8.8	105.7	157.6
Co(DHP) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂	12.2	110.5	172.4
Ni(DHP) ₂ (NH ₃) ₂	13.6	120.4	187.3
Fe(DHP) ₂ (CH ₃ NH ₂) ₂	9.2	120.1	160.2
Co(DHP) ₂ (CH ₃ NH ₂) ₂	12.1	128.2	177.1
Ni(DHP) ₂ (CH ₃ NH ₂) ₂	13.4	134.6	193.4
Fe(DHP) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂) ₂	9.2	124.5	164.2
Co(DHP) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂) ₂	12.6	130.1	182.5
Ni(DHP) ₂ (C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂) ₂	13.8	139.6	197.6
Fe(DHP) ₂ (C ₅ H ₅ N) ₂	8.8	100.1	152.5
Co(DHP) ₂ (C ₅ H ₅ N) ₂	12.1	104.1	169.6
Ni(DHP) ₂ (C ₅ H ₅ N) ₂	13.4	109.6	183.4

* All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and metal analyses.

A broad IR band of free DHP at 3200 cm⁻¹ indicates hydrogen bonding which disappeared in all the metal complexes, showing simultaneous deprotonation and the for-

mation of M–O bond at 3-position. A strong band at 1625 cm⁻¹ (C=O) shifted to lower side in the complexes, which suggests that the ligand coordinates to metal through oxygen of carbonyl group at 2-position. A relatively weak band at 3400 cm⁻¹ observed in free DHP and attributed to ν_{N–H} of α-pyridone like structure of DHP, remained unchanged in the complexes, suggesting its non-involvement in coordination. Appearance of ν_{N–H} vibration at 3240–3280 cm⁻¹ in complexes indicates coordination of NH₃/CH₃NH₂/C₂H₅NH₂. In the case of pyridine complexes, a change in the characteristic ring vibration band (1460 cm⁻¹) of pyridine to high frequencies suggests that N of pyridine is bonded to the metal atom⁴. A band at 405–460 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes shows the bonding (M–O) of oxygen atoms of DHP with metal. A band at 355–380 cm⁻¹ found in complexes shows the M–N bonding⁵, N being a donor atom from NH₃/CH₃NH₂/C₂H₅NH₂.

The electronic spectral band at 11240–11320 cm⁻¹ observed in the spectrum of the Fe^{II} complex may be attributed to ⁵T_{2g} → ⁵E_g transition which supports octahedral geometry around metal ion⁶. The bands observed at 8800–8840, 17020–17060 and 20020–20110 cm⁻¹ in the Co^{II} complexes are assigned to transitions ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴A_{2g}(F) (ν₂) and ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{1g}(P) (ν₃), respectively, suggesting that there is an octahedral geometry around Co^{II} ion⁷. The Ni^{II} complexes show three bands at 10200–10400, 16600–16680 and 25000–25040 cm⁻¹, assigned to ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(F) (ν₁), ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{1g}(F) (ν₂) and ³A_{2g}(F) → ³T_{2g}(P) (ν₃), respectively. These bands suggest a typical octahedral geometry for Ni^{II} complexes⁶.

Various ligand field parameters such as 10Dq, B and β were calculated for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes. The nephelauxetic ratio (β) for Co^{II} (0.726–0.734) and Ni^{II} (0.662–

0.694 cm^{-1}) complexes is less than unity in each case indicating partial covalent character in metal-ligand bond.

TG, DTG, DTA and DSC results follow a similar pattern for all the complexes. TG curves show that these complexes decompose in two steps. The first step decomposition at 173–303° corresponds to the loss of two molecules of nitrogen donor ligands, i.e., $\text{NH}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2/\text{pyridine}$, and the second step decomposition at 339–358° corresponds to the loss of DHP and formation of metal oxide. In the case of the Fe^{II} and Co^{II} complexes, the weight of metal oxide corresponds to the formation of Fe_3O_4 and Co_3O_4 and in case of Ni^{II} , NiO .

The kinetic parameters, apparent activation energy and order of reaction for the first step thermal decomposition of Fe^{II} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes have been determined by graphical methods of Coats and Redfern⁸. The values of kinetic parameters are given in Table 1. In each case, the first thermal decomposition has the order of reaction as 1. The activation energy values follow the order with respect to metal as $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} < \text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$. If we compare the activation energy with respect to nitrogen donors (NH_3 , CH_3NH_2 , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}$) the order is $\text{Py} < \text{NH}_3 < \text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2 < \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$. The magnitude of these values is a compromise between two opposing factors : basicity of the ligand and the strain.

DTG curves of all the complexes are of similar nature. In each case, two peaks are obtained and the area under the second DTG curve is higher than that under the first DTG curve. On this basis it is inferred that decomposition takes places at two stages, the first decomposition involves the loss of two nitrogen donor molecules and the second one, the loss of two DHP molecules and redox processes.

The TG and DTG data are supplemented by DTA and DSC studies. DTA curve in each case shows two peaks : an endothermic peak attributed to the liberation of two molecules of $\text{NH}_3/\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2/\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2/\text{Py}$, and an exothermic peak assigned due to simultaneous decomposition, oxidation-reduction processes of the complex. The t_{max} of endothermic peak lies in the range $251 \pm 22^\circ$ and that of exothermic peak at $403 \pm 23^\circ$. From the values of heat of reaction (Table 1) it is observed that the order with respect to metal ion is $\text{Fe}^{\text{II}} < \text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}}$, and that with respect to the nitrogen donors is $\text{Py} < \text{NH}_3 < \text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2 < \text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2$.

DSC curves show only one endothermic peak due to recording of DSC upto 350° temperature only. Heat of reaction for endothermic transitions are given in Table 1. The order of heats of reaction with respect to the metal and ligand is same as found in the case of DTA. However, there are differences in DTA and DSC values which are

due to the use of different atmosphere for DTA (nitrogen) and DSC (oxygen). The t_{max} of endothermic peak lies in the range $132 \pm 13^\circ$.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. DHP (Aldrich) was used. A mixture of aqueous solution of the metal salt (50 μmol), DHP (100 μmol) and a nitrogen donor ligand (100 μmol) (pH maintained at pH ~9.0) was refluxed for 1–1.5 h. On cooling the complexes precipitated out in each case which were washed and dried in desiccator.

The metal contents in the complexes were determined following standard methods. Analyses for carbon and hydrogen were performed in micro analytical lab. Nitrogen contents were determined by Kjeldahl's method. A Toshniwal conductometer was used for measuring molar conductance in nitrobenzene. Electronic spectra (nujol) were run of Beckman DU-64 spectrophotometer and IR spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. TG and DTG measurements were carried out with 9900 a Du Pont 9900 thermoanalyser. DTA and DSC measurements were carried out with Leads and Northup DTA unit and 910 DSC module, respectively. In TG, DTG and DTA nitrogen atmosphere and in DSC oxygen atmosphere were maintained with flow rates of 60–70 ml min^{-1} (TG, DTG, DTA) and 50–60 ml min^{-1} (DSC).

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